

TRANSLATING AUDIO DESCRIPTION FROM SPANISH INTO CHINESE: A RECEPTION STUDY

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Audio description (AD) in China has developed largely through volunteer-led initiatives. Recent copyright-related legal developments may nevertheless signal a gradual move toward clearer regulation, standardisation, and professionalisation (Liu, 2023). A key aim of this transition is to expand the quantity, variety, and quality of AD while reducing production time and cost. Yet the sector continues to face a shortage of trained AD scriptwriters (Tor-Carroggio, 2020).

Against this backdrop, this study positions AD translation as a form of indirect translation in which a pre-existing Spanish AD script functions as a bridge template between the audiovisual source and a new Chinese AD. This workflow is intended to increase AD provision in China both quantitatively and qualitatively. Comparable approaches have been explored through reception studies in other contexts, with encouraging results (López Vera, 2006; Jankowska, 2015). However, because AD is strongly target-oriented, such mediated transfer is likely to require careful localisation to ensure cultural and pragmatic accessibility (Remael & Vercauteren, 2010; Jankowska, Miłk & Fryer, 2017).

A reception study with Chinese AD users was conducted to examine acceptance of three AD versions for the Spanish film *The Invisible Guest* (Oriol Paulo, 2016): (1) an original Chinese AD written from scratch (Chinese AD); (2) a Chinese AD translated from an existing Spanish AD (Translated AD); and (3) a translated Chinese AD further localised according to a set of localisation guidelines (Localised AD). Results show only one statistically significant difference between the original Chinese AD and the Translated AD regarding overall satisfaction with quality. By contrast, AD version did not produce a significant difference in comprehension or perceived presence.

These findings suggest that AD translation can be a viable, resource-efficient pathway for expanding Chinese AD provision, and that localisation may further enhance user satisfaction. More broadly, the study positions AD translation as a productive site for investigating indirect translation through a user-centred lens.

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